

Preparation and characterization of doped $\text{Sr}_{2}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ hexaferrite: An efficient heterogeneous catalyst for one pot synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridine derivatives[†]

A. S. Aswar* and C. A. Ladole

Department of Chemistry, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, Maharashtra, India

E-mail: aswaranand@gmail.com

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A clean and efficient method has been developed for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridine derivatives using aromatic aldehyde, ethyl acetoacetate, and ammonium acetate using cobalt doped strontium hexaferrite under microwave irradiation conditions. This process offers an easy and efficient synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridine derivatives with high yields. The advantages of this protocol are operational simplicity, its greenness with respect to mild reaction conditions, short reaction time, maximum yields of products, simple workup and an environmentally benign nature. The cobalt doped strontium hexaferrite catalyst was synthesized by the solution combustion method. The prepared catalyst was characterized by XRD, FT-IR, SEM and TG/DTA analysis. Furthermore, the catalyst could be reused up to four cycles without significant loss in activity. The synthesized compounds were confirmed using FT-IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic data and melting points compared with reported values.

Keywords: 1,4-Dihydropyridines, Hantzsch reaction, microwave irradiation, $\text{Sr}_{2}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$.

Introduction

1,4-Dihydropyridines are an important class of nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds having extensive applications in the synthesis of drugs and exhibit attractive pharmacological profiles¹. These compounds possess a range of biological activities such as a group of calcium modulators bronchodilator, vasodilator, antiatherosclerotic, geroprotective hepatoprotective, antitumor, antidiabetic agents, particularly hypertension and angina pectoris. The various activities of 1,4-DHPs derivatives frequently derives from the functional groups substituted on the 1,4-dihydropyridines moiety. On the other hand, multicomponent reactions are important synthetic tools that can be useful in the preparation of biologically active compounds due to their intrinsic atom economy, selectivity, simplicity and energy efficiency²⁻⁴. In order to achieve the green chemistry principles, the reaction was carried out in heterogeneous environment to create more economical and eco-friendly route⁵, as reusability and recovery of heterogeneous catalyst is simple⁶. The effective strategy offers considerable advantageous over classical stepwise methods, allowing the formation of sev-

eral bonds and construction of complex molecules from simple precursors in a single synthetic procedure without the essential requirement for isolation of intermediates⁷⁻¹⁰.

In the recent year microwave assisted organic reaction has emerged as new tool in organic synthesis. Important advantage of this technology include highly accelerated rate of the reaction, reduction in reaction time with an improvement in the yield and quality of the product. Now day's technique is considered as an important approach toward green chemistry, because this technique is more environmentally friendly¹¹⁻¹³. Conventional method of organic synthesis usually need longer heating time, tedious apparatus setup, which result in higher cost of process and the excessive use of solvents/reagents lead to environmental pollution¹⁴. The 1,4-dihydropyridine derivatives have greater attention due to its biological activities, ranging from anti-microbial¹⁵, antiviral¹⁶, anti-cancer¹⁷, anti-oxidant¹⁸, anti-coagulant¹⁹, anti-tubercular agents²⁰, and calcium channel modulation agents²¹. 1,4-DHPs are broadly synthesized using Hantzsch method, that involves one pot cyclocondensation of dicarbonyls, aldehydes and ammonium acetate/primary amine/ammonia either in

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refluxing with acetic acid or alcohol leading to low yields with longer reaction time. In recent decades, several modified catalytic methods have been developed for the synthesis of 1,4-DPHs such as γ - Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles²², cellulose sulfuric acid²³, cadmium chloride²⁴, ionic liquid²⁵, and $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_3$ ²⁶ have been used. All methods, however, are associated with some drawbacks such as longer time, unsatisfactory yields, difficulty in handling of reagents. Hence, the development of an efficient method seemed to be of prime importance. Consequently, we targeted to alter the reaction of Hantzsch 1,4-DPHs to make it more convenient and extremely efficient method using microwave irradiation technique using nanocrystalline catalyst. Moreover, microwave irradiation method has become more popular due to its efficiency and minimized hazard of pollution to achieve eco-friendly process. In view of the importance associated with this class of compounds, here we report the synthesis and characterization of 1,4-dihydropyridine derivatives using $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ hexaferrite as catalyst in varying amounts for Hantzsch reaction by microwave irradiation method and predict its reaction mechanism.

Results and discussion

Catalytic characterization:

The X-ray diffraction patterns of strontium hexaferrite and cobalt ferrite without or with doping synthesized by solution combustion method are shown in Fig. 1. This results show that strontium and doped strontium hexaferrite have a similarity to the data peaks. The indexed XRD peaks are well matched with standard JCPDS card no. 33-1340. However, comparing to the inset of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$, the characteristic diffraction peaks of XRD pattern, (110), (107), (114), (201), (203), (205), (217), (220), and (300) observed in the $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$

Fig. 1. XRD spectrum of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ and $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ hexaferrite.

ferrites. Therefore, the phase structure of cobalt-doped strontium ferrite is M-type hexagonal ferrite. The crystallite size of synthesized particle was found to be 22.71 nm according to Scherer formula.

The SEM micrograph exhibit porous and agglomerated microstructure with irregular shape in conventionally calcinated pure and doped strontium hexaferrite and depicted in Fig. 2. The size varies in the range 1–10 μm and it is not well defined in shape. The micrograph of ferrite shows that the particles are embedded in a sheet like structure due to the presence of impurities or incomplete reaction in sample as confirmed from X-ray diffraction analysis.

Fig. 2. SEM images of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (S1) and $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (C1) hexaferrite.

The thermograms of both $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ and $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ ferrites show gradual continuous weight loss up to 100°C and exhibit one step continuous pyrolysis without any break leaving only 14.58% of the substance (Fig. 3). The DTA curve shows endothermic reaction. The weight loss corresponds to the removal of chemisorbed water from the surface hydroxyl groups as the system gets more and more dehydrated into the oxide spinel phase.

The FT-IR spectra of both strontium and cobalt doped strontium hexaferrite in the range 450–4000 cm^{-1} are presented in Fig. 4. For comparison of strontium ferrites obtained by solution combustion method with addition of cobalt with nominal composition the large band around 3398 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching mode of H_2O molecules and the band corresponding to the bending vibrations was observed at 1632 cm^{-1} . From the spectra, it can be seen the absorption bands at around 461, 536, 551 and 598 cm^{-1} corresponds to typical M-O vibrations bands of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ ²⁷.

Fig. 3. TG/DTA analysis of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (S1) and $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (C1) hexaferrite.

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectra of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (S1) and $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (C1) hexaferrite.

To optimize the reaction conditions, we have checked the three component condensation reaction of benzaldehyde, ethyl acetoacetate and ammonium acetate in the presence of catalyst, (10 wt.%) of $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ using microwave irradiation method. The reaction was completed within 7 min to give diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (product **4a**), with an excellent yields as shown in Scheme 1. To improve product yields and to optimize re-

action conditions, the reaction was carried out in absence and presence of varying amount of catalyst in different solvents and conditions (Table 1). The yield was only 18% in absence of catalyst under microwave irradiation conditions in 21 min with recovery of starting material (Entry 1, Table 1). The same reaction was performed in presence of strontium cobalt hexaferrite under the same conditions with varying amount of the catalyst, yield increased up to 95% (Table 1) at 10 wt.% of catalyst $\text{Sr}_2\text{Co}_8\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ and a significant improvement was observed in the reaction time and product yield. This 10 wt.% of catalyst was used in each successive reaction and the time duration ranges from 7 to 15 min.

The effect of solvents on the reaction with various solvent systems such as water, ethanol, toluene and THF were screened at different temperatures; it was slow and produced by products (Table 1). The catalyst strontium cobalt-hexaferrite was found to be superior over other known catalysts like CuI NPs, $\text{SiO}_2\text{-NaHSO}_4$, Co NPs as it gives high product yield in minimum possible time (Table 2). The reaction condition was then optimized by conducting the reaction

Table 1. Optimization of reaction condition for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines and their solvents effect on product formation (**4a**)^a

Entry	Catalyst (wt%)	Solvents/Condition	Time (min)/Yield ^b (%)
1	Without catalyst	Solvent free/microwave	21/18
2	3	Solvent free/microwave	18/48
3	6	Solvent free/microwave	14/83
4	10	Solvent free/microwave	7/95
5	10	EtOH/reflux	120/67
6	10	H ₂ O/reflux	120/53
7	10	Toluene/reflux	120/68
8	10	THF/reflux	120/71

^aReactions carried out at 10 mmol scale with molar ratio of benzaldehyde:ethyl acetoacetate:ammonium acetate = 1:2:1, ^bisolated yield.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines using benzaldehyde, ethyl acetoacetate and ammonium acetate.

Table 2. Comparative study with different catalyst

Entry	Catalyst	Amount (wt%)	Molar ratio ^a	Condition/solvent	Time (min)/ yield ^b (%)	Ref.
1	CuI NPs	2	1:2:1	Stirring at 80°C/ ethanol	18/88	28
2	SiO ₂ -NaHSO ₄	5	1:2:2	Stirring/CH ₃ CN	300/90	29
3	Co NPs	50	1:1:1:1.5	Stirring/solvent free	8/95	30
4	Sr ₂ Co ₈ Fe ₁₂ O ₁₉	10	1:2:1	Microwave/solvent free	7/95	This work

^aMolar ratio of benzaldehyde:ethyl acetoacetate:ammonium acetate, ^bisolated yield.

with various aromatic aldehydes, ethyl acetoacetate and ammonium acetate using Sr₂Co₈Fe₁₂O₁₉ catalyst and results are summarized in Table 3. It was also observed that, a wide variety of aromatic aldehydes bearing electron-releasing, as well as electron-withdrawing, substituent reacted smoothly to give the corresponding 1,4-dihydropyridines in moderate to excellent yields (87–95%). Acid sensitive aldehydes such as cinnamaldehyde and aldehydes containing Cl, OH, NO₂ and OCH₃ react very efficiently to give corresponding product without forming any side product (Table 3). Also the reaction was investigated at different temperatures (80–120°C) under microwave irradiation.

The synthesis of diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate as a model reaction was

performed and the catalyst was recovered in ethanol and reused for four more cycles (Table 4). In order to provide evidence for this reaction a proposed mechanism is suggested as in Fig. 5.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and solvents were distilled prior to their used. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker Avance (400 MHz) spectrometer using CDCl₃ as a solvent. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 10.4.2 FTIR spectrophotometer. Microwave irradiation experiments were performed in scientific microwave synthesizer system supplied by Ragatech Electronics having maximum power output of 700 W and 2450

Table 3. Synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines using Sr₂Co₈Fe₁₂O₁₉ catalyst

Entry	Product	Substrate R	Substrate x	Reaction time (min)	Yield (%)	M.p. (lit. M.p.)/°C
1	4a	Ph	OC ₂ H ₅	7	95	158 (158–160)
2	4b	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	OC ₂ H ₅	15	90	154 (153–155)
3	4c	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	OC ₂ H ₅	10	92	174 (172–175)
4	4d	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	OC ₂ H ₅	12	90	165 (165–167)
5	4e	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	OC ₂ H ₅	11	91	146 (145–146)
6	4f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	15	91	101 (101–103)
7	4g	2-OH ₃ -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	14	90	205 (206–208)
8	4h	2-Furyl	OC ₂ H ₅	14	87	160 (160–161)

^aReaction conditions: aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol); ethyl acetoacetate (2 mmol); ammonium acetate (1 mmol); Sr₂Co₈Fe₁₂O₁₉ catalyst (10 wt.%). All products are known and were identified by their melting point, IR and ¹³C NMR and ¹H NMR spectra according to literature.

Table 4. Reusability of catalyst

Entry	Catalyst recovery ^a (%)	Yield ^b (%)
1	–	95
2	92	91
3	90	90
4	89	88
5	88	87

^aCatalyst recovered by filtration and washing with ethanol, ^byields of the product.

Fig. 5. Mechanism of formation of 1,4-dihydropyridines using catalyst.

MHz frequency with 10 power levels at given temperature. The SEM was recorded with JEOL, JSM-6390LV. The XRD data was done on a Bruker AXS-D8 advanced X-ray powder diffractometer with Cu K_α line ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range from 10–90°C. The thermal analysis was made on a Perkin-Elmer STA 6000 instrument. The reaction progress was monitored and purity of products was checked by TLC. Melting points were determined on a quality make digital melting point apparatus and are not corrected.

General procedure for preparation of catalyst:

The SrFe₁₂O₁₉ and cobalt doped strontium particles were synthesized using solution combustion method. Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O and Sr(NO₃)₂ were dissolved in de-ionized water to form an aqueous solution of 0.1 M. An aqueous solution of citric acid was mixed with metal nitrates solution. The molar ratio of solutes in the solution was Sr²⁺_(x)Co_(1-x): Fe³⁺:C₃H₄(OH)(COOH)₃ = 1:12:19. The pH of solution was adjusted to 7 by adding NH₄OH. It was refluxed at 90°C for 2 h to allow the carboxyl groups of citric acid to completely

chelate metallic ions in the solution. It was heated in microwave at 200°C for half an hour to obtain the solid precursor. It was calcinated in muffle furnace at 500°C, for 4 h at a heating rate of 10°C/min and hexaferrite powder was obtained.

General procedure for preparation of 1,4-dihydropyridines (4a-h):

To a mixture of an aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (2 mmol), ammonium acetate (1 mmol) and catalytic amount of strontium cobalt hexaferrite (10 wt.%) were mixed in 100 mL round bottom flask and irradiated in microwave (350 W) for appropriate period of time. After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC using hexane: ethyl acetate in 6:4 ratio (v/v) and mixture was diluted with ethanol (20 mL), filtered and washed with ethanol (3×10 mL) to remove the catalyst. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain a solid product. It was slurred in water (3×20 mL), filtered and recrystallized from ethanol. The catalyst was dried and recycled for the next runs. All the products were confirmed using FT-IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic data and melting points compared with reported values.

Spectral data for respective products:

Diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (Table 3, product 4a):

IR (KBr): ν 3342, 3060, 1687, 1651, 1488, 1323, 1299, 1211, 1123, 1091, 1020, 702 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.23 (t, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.31 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 4.08 (m, 4H, 2CH₂), 4.98 (s, 1H, CH), 5.78 (s, 1H, NH), 7.11–7.29 (m, 5H, ArH); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 14.25, 19.57, 39.64, 59.73, 104.19, 126.10, 127.83, 128.01, 143.85, 147.77, 167.65.

Diethyl 4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (Table 3, product 4b):

IR (KBr): ν 3301, 3232, 2985, 1707, 1693, 1498, 1264, 1126, 733 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.64 (t, 6H, 2CH₂CH₃), 2.27 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 3.07 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 4.13 (m, 4H, 2CH₂), 4.90 (s, 1H, OH), 5.47 (s, 1H, NH), 7.17–7.26 (m, 4H, ArH).

Diethyl 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (Table 3, product 4c):

IR (KBr): ν 3341, 2984, 1687, 1648, 1488, 1300, 1119, 834, 748 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.24 (t, 6H, 2CH₂CH₃), 2.28 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 3.73 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 4.04 (m, 4H, OCH₂), 4.93 (s, 1H, CH), 6.07 (s, 1H, NH), 6.75–7.20 (m, 4H, ArH);

^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): δ 14.29, 19.14, 38.75, 55.14, 59.71, 104.17, 113.20, 128.94, 140.43, 143.92, 157.88, 167.85.

Diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (Table 3, product 4d):

IR (KBr): ν 3343, 2991, 1704, 1643, 1523, 1483, 1369, 1210, 1114, 787, 703 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 1.22 (t, 6H, 2 CH_3), 2.35 (s, 6H, 2 CH_3), 4.13 (q, 4H, OCH_2), 5.10 (s, 1H, CH), 6.09 (s, 1H, NH), 7.27–8.13 (m, 4H, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): δ 14.23, 19.50, 39.96, 59.99, 103.23, 121.31, 123.09, 128.60, 134.52, 144.91, 148.15, 149.98, 167.18.

Conclusion

We have reported simple and efficient protocol for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyrimidines derivatives by using cobalt doped strontium hexaferrite under microwave irradiation condition. The catalyst has many advantages such as reusability, recovery, insoluble in most organic solvents, being eco-friendly and green process catalysts. The catalyst is recovered by filtration and reused at least four times without significant loss in catalytic activity and characterized by XRD, FT-IR, SEM and TG/DTA. The method offers several advantages including its greenness with respect to mild reaction conditions, easy workup, short reaction time and high yield.

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References

- Q. Fan, P. Li and H. Yan, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A*, 2018, **358**, 51.
- A. Domling, W. Wang and K. Wang, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 3083.
- C. D. Graaff, E. Ruijter and R. V. A. Orru, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **41**, 3969.
- S. Brauch, S. S. Berkel and B. Westermann, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2013, **42**, 4948.
- S. Maddila, S. Gorle, S. Shabalala, O. Oyetade, S. N. Maddila, P. Lavanya and S. B. Jonnalagadda, *Arab. J. Chem.*, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2016.04.016.
- R. Pagadala, S. Maddila, V. Moodley, W. E. Van Zyl and S. B. Jonnalagadda, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2014, **55**, 4006.
- J. Yang, C. Jiang, J. Yang, C. Qian and D. Fang, *Green Chem. Lett. Rev.*, 2013, **6**, 262.
- S. N. Maddila, S. Maddila, W. E. Van Zyl and S. B. Jonnalagadda, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 37360.
- Y. Bai, J. Zeng, J. Ma, B. K. Gorityala and X. W. Liu, *J. Comb. Chem.*, 2010, **12**, 696.
- C. A. Ladole, N. G. Salunkhe, R. S. Bhaskar and A. S. Aswar, *Eur. J. Chem.*, 2014, **5(1)**, 122.
- J. P. Li, P. Z. Zheng, J. G. Zhu, R. J. Liu and G. R. Qu, *Braz. J. Chem. Eng.*, 2007, **24(4)**, 471.
- M. A. Aweda, R. O. K. Meindinyo, S. O. Gbeneditse and A. Z. Ibitoye, *Adv. Appl. Sci. Res.*, 2011, **2(2)**, 246.
- J. Safari, S. H. Banitaba and S. S. Samiei, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2009, **121**, 481.
- J. J. Vanden Eynde and A. Mayence, *Molecule*, 2003, **8**, 381.
- F. Lentz, M. Hemmer, N. Reiling and A. Hilgeroth, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2016, **26**, 5896.
- H. Adibi, H. A. Samimi and M. Beygzadeh, *Catal. Commun.*, 2007, **8**, 2119.
- F. Shekari, H. Sadeghpour, K. Javidnia, L. Saso, F. Nazari, O. Firuzi and R. Miri, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 2015, **746**, 233.
- A. M. Vijesh, A. M. Isloor, S. K. Peethambar, K. N. Shivananda, T. Arulmoli and N. A. Isloor, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 5591.
- R. S. Kumar, A. Idhayadhulla, A. J. Abdul Nasser and J. Selvin, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 804.
- M. Khoshneviszadeh, N. Edraki, K. Javidnia, A. Alborzi, B. Pourabbas, J. Mardaneh and R. Miri, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 1579.
- D. Schaller, M. G. Gunduz, F. X. Zhang, G. W. Zamponi and G. Wolber, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2018, **155**, 1.
- W. Hea, Z. Fangb, K. Zhang, T. Tu, N. Lv, C. Qiu and K. Guo, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2018, **331**, 161.
- J. Safari, S. H. Banitaba and S. D. Khalili, *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.*, 2011, **335**, 46.
- Y. Venkateswarlu, S. R. Kumar and P. Leelavathi, *Int. J. Ind. Chem.*, 2012, **3(18)**, 1.
- A. Shaabani, A. H. Rezayan, A. Rahmati and M. Sharif, *Monatshefte fur Chemie*, 2006, **137**, 77.
- S. Pednekar, R. Bhalerao and N. Ghadge, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2013, **125(3)**, 615.
- W. Chen, Q. Liu, X. Zhu and M. Fu, *RSC Adv.*, 2017, **7**, 40650.
- J. S. Ghomi, A. Ziarati and R. Teymuri, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **33(8)**, 2679.
- C. M. Adharvana and K. Syamasundar, *Catal. Commun.*, 2005, **6(9)**, 624.
- J. Safari, S. H. Banitaba and S. D. Khalili, *Chin. J. Catal.*, 2011, **32**, 1850.